

GC-MS method development and validation for the determination of Short Chain Fatty Acids in human feces

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ABSTRACT

Short Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs), the end products of microbial fermentation of dietary fibers, appear to be key mediators of the beneficial effects elicited by the gut microbiome and have been shown to exert multiple effects on metabolism. In this study, we developed and validated a sensitive, accurate, and reproducible GC-MS method for the simultaneous quantification of SCFAs (Acetic acid (C₂), propionic acid (C₃), butyric acid (C₄), isobutyric acid and isovaleric acid) in human feces. Sample preparation was simplified while maintaining robustness, following systematic evaluation of homogenization, extraction solvents, and acidification conditions. The optimized method demonstrated high analytical performance, with limits of detection ranging from 0.01 to 0.52 μmol/g and good precision and accuracy in accordance with FDA and EMA bioanalytical guidelines. Stability studies revealed that SCFAs remain stable in acidified fecal samples for up to 10 days without cold-chain requirements, while -80 °C storage was optimal for long-term preservation and 4 °C suitable for short-term handling. The applicability of the method was confirmed through analysis of samples collected from healthy volunteers. Overall, the developed approach provides a practical, high-throughput, and scalable tool for SCFA analysis, supporting applications in clinical research, metabolomics, and large-scale microbiome studies.

1. Introduction

Gut microbial balance has been linked to various diseases and overall human health. Several studies have revealed how gut microbiota can influence basic biological processes, including nutrient uptake, metabolism and immunity, through several mechanisms [1]. Short Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) are volatile organic acids and constitute the end products of indigestible dietary fermentation by gut microbiota [2]. They consist of one to six carbon atoms and are found in aliphatic or branched-chain conformation. Acetic acid (C₂), propionic acid (C₃) and butyric acid (C₄) are the most abundant, with an approximate molar ratio of 60:20:20, respectively [3]. While SCFAs are mainly produced from carbohydrates' fermentation, amino acids derived from protein

breakdown, can transform into branched-SCFAs (BSCFAs), such as isobutyric and isovaleric acids, which however account for a very small fraction (5%) of the total SCFAs production [4].

In healthy conditions, gut microbiota exists in a state of symbiosis with the host, which ensures microbial balance and therefore optimal metabolic interactions. However, in disease states, disruptions in microbiota composition, known as dysbiosis, can lead to altered SCFAs concentrations [1,5]. Therefore, SCFAs have emerged as promising biomarkers for the emergence and progression of various diseases, including inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), colorectal cancer, autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and metabolic disorders. Determining fecal SCFAs levels could provide a non-invasive approach for assessing gut health and identifying diseases related to

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microbiota disruptions [5].

SCFAs demonstrate their physiological effects through several mechanisms, particularly by serving as the main energy source for colonocytes, but also by regulating gut pH and influencing metabolism and immunity of the host [6]. Their biological activity is greatly mediated by the activation of free fatty acids receptors (FFARs), including G-protein coupled receptors (GPR41 and GPR43), which exert diverse functions regarding gut physiology, such as the regulation of gut motility, the modulation of immune responses and the promotion of gut hormones [7,8]. In addition, SCFAs appear to inhibit histone deacetylases (HDACs), resulting in potential gene expression modulation and thus affecting brain function and behavior [9].

Given their biological significance, accurate determination of SCFAs in biological samples is crucial for understanding their role in health and disease. However, the analysis of SCFAs opposes several challenges, mainly due to their physicochemical properties, such as high volatility and susceptibility to degradation, but also due to potential matrix effects, affecting accuracy, sensitivity and reproducibility. An array of analytical techniques, notably liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) [10–13], gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) [14–18], capillary electrophoresis (CE) [19–21], and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy [22,23], have been used to overcome these limitations. From these techniques, the most widely used for the measurements of SCFAs is GC-MS, given its high sensitivity and separation efficiency. Most of the methods developed so far carry out derivatization procedures for the accurate quantitation of SCFAs, thus introducing more steps and limitations in the analytical procedure, as they require moisture-free conditions, while the high volatility of SCFAs prevents the use of evaporation, as it may lead to their loss [14–16]. Extracts of SCFAs can be analyzed directly when using appropriate capillary columns, like WAX columns, eliminating the need for derivatization of the analytes [18]. In this study, we aimed to develop a new analytical method omitting the step of derivatization, simplifying sample preparation, so that it can be applied in routine analytical environments and clinical settings, and presented an optimized method for SCFAs GC-MS profiling.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Ethyl acetate, diethyl ether and methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE) (HPLC grade) were obtained from CHEM-LAB NV (Zedelgem, Belgium). Hydrochloric acid 37% (HCl), sulfuric acid 95% (H₂SO₄) and phosphoric acid 85% (H₃PO₄) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck Darmstadt, Germany). Ultra-pure water was obtained from a demineralizing water system (Hydrolab, Poland). Acetic acid, propionic acid, isobutyric acid, butyric acid, isovaleric acid, valeric acid and internal standard [¹³C₂]-acetic acid were of great purity ≥ 99% and acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2. Preparation of standards and calibration curves

Stock solutions of the SCFAs were prepared in water at concentrations ranging from 1000 to 10,000 mgL⁻¹ and stored at -20 °C until use.

Working solutions were prepared from stock solutions by appropriate dilutions with water and finally eight different mixtures of analytes were prepared. The final concentrations of the calibrants used for method development and validation are listed in Table S1.

Two series of calibration standards were prepared to select the most suitable calibration model: an “external” calibration curve using standard solutions in neat solvent, and a “standard addition” curve, where known quantities of the standard were spiked into the real samples. The calibration range was established based on the expected endogenous concentrations of each compound in fecal samples, as reported in the literature [13,19].

2.3. Optimisation of sample extraction

To optimize the extraction of Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) from fecal matrices for GC/MS analysis, a comprehensive series of method development experiments was conducted. Following homogenization and variability assessment, extraction conditions of SCFAs were systematically investigated using standard mixtures in water at LQC, MQC and HQC concentration levels (Section 2.6.2 Extraction Recovery). Four organic solvents commonly employed for SCFA extraction, such as ethyl acetate, hexane, diethyl ether, and methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE), were compared to determine the solvent providing the highest extraction efficiency. In order to increase the extraction recovery, sample acidification before extraction was further explored using various acidifying reagents, including 3.7% v/v HCl in methanol, 0.5 M H₂SO₄, concentrated HCl (37% g/v and 5 M), and phosphoric acid (85% v/v and 15% v/v). Based on preliminary results, the acidification step was refined by testing different volumes (10–50 µL) of 15% H₃PO₄. The optimum extraction conditions were further applied to human fecal samples after systematic study of homogenisation procedure and intra sample variability. The homogenization procedure was optimized using 50 mg of sample, to ensure complete sample dispersion and reproducible extraction efficiency. Three approaches were evaluated: (i) two homogenization cycles of 30 s each at 6 m/s using a Bead Mill homogenizer, (ii) a single 30 s cycle at 6 m/s using a Bead Mill homogenizer followed by a 30 min ultrasonic bath, and (iii) a 30 min ultrasonic bath alone. Intra-sample variability was assessed using fecal samples collected from healthy volunteers. Three replicate subsamples (50 mg each) were obtained from four predefined regions of the stool designated as top, middle, bottom, and edge and concentrations of SCFAs were compared against these from homogenised samples. These designations were defined to represent distinct spatial regions of a single fecal mass. This sampling strategy was employed to evaluate potential intra-sample heterogeneity in SCFAs concentrations across different regions of the same specimen.

2.4. Analytical conditions and instrumentation

GC/MS analysis was performed using an EVOQ 4566 GC-TQ-MS triple quadrupole system (Bruker, Bremen, Germany), equipped with a CTC autosampler and a PTV injector operated through Compass Hystar software. Data processing was performed with MSWS8 software. GC separation was performed on a HP-INNOWAX capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm, 0.25 µm film thickness) (Agilent Technologies). Initial column temperature was set at 35 °C for 2 min and was increased with a rate of 10 °C /min to 155 °C, where temperature was held constant for 2 min. Next the temperature was increased to 250 °C at a rate of 25 °C /min and held constant for another 2 min. The total analysis time was 21.8 min with a solvent delay set at 10.5 min. Helium was used as carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. Splitless injection with 1 µL volume was performed, while the injector temperature was kept constant at 220 °C throughout the analysis. The mass spectrometer (MS) was operated in electron impact ionization mode (70 eV, ion source temperature: 230 °C, transfer line temperature: 250 °C). The autosampler syringe was washed before and after each injection with three cycles of methanol.

To establish the retention times of the analytes of interest, injections were performed in full-scan mode (20–100 amu, 250 ms acquisition frequency). The retention time of each chromatographic peak was subsequently verified by matching its MS spectrum with the corresponding reference spectrum from the NIST database (NIST17 Library). Compound identification was performed using the NIST/EPA/NIH Mass Spectral Library (NIST 17) and the NIST MS Search Program (version 2.3, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA). Quantification of SCFAs was carried out in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode, focusing on the most intense ion for each compound. The monitored ions were *m/z* 60 for acetic acid, *m/z* 74 for propionic acid, *m/z* 41 for isobutyric acid, *m/z* 60 for butyric acid, *m/z* 60 for

isovaleric acid, and m/z 60 for valeric acid. For the labeled internal standard, [$^{13}\text{C}_2$]-acetic acid, the target ion was m/z 62.

2.5. Sample preparation

For each sample, 50 mg of feces were weighed and mixed with 1 mL of Milli-Q ultrapure water. Subsequently, they were homogenized at a speed of 6 m/s for two 30-second intervals using a Bead Mill homogenizer (VWR Chemicals). The homogenized mixture was then centrifuged at $6500 \times g$ for 10 min. A 100 μL aliquot of the supernatant (fecal water) was transferred to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube, and 20 μL of 15% H_3PO_4 were added to adjust the pH of the solution to a value below two ($\text{pH} < 2$). To extract the SCFAs, 400 μL of MTBE were added to the acidified fecal water homogenate, followed by vortex mixing for 5 min. Finally, 120 μL of the MTBE layer were transferred into a GC/MS vial for analysis. Optimum sample preparation workflow is illustrated in Fig. 1.

2.6. Method validation

The analytical method was validated in accordance with the guidelines of the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the ICH M10 guidelines for the bioanalysis of endogenous compounds [24,25]. Validation parameters included selectivity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, linearity, extraction recovery, matrix effect, and stability. Special consideration was given to stability of SCFAs in human feces under different storage conditions, simulating real-world scenarios of collection and transportation.

2.6.1. Calibration, linearity, limit of detection and quantification

A calibration curve prepared in water was compared with a matrix-matched calibration curve generated by fortifying a pooled fecal sample at concentration levels ranging from 1.56 to 199.8 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for acetic acid, 0.63–80.99 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for propionic acid, 0.43–13.62 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for isobutyric acid, 0.7–45.40 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for butyric acid, 0.03–3.92 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ for isovaleric and valeric acids. The equivalence between the two calibration approaches was evaluated by assessing the parallelism of the curves through comparison of their slopes. Slope ratios with values between

0.80 and 1.2 were considered acceptable, indicating negligible interference from the matrix.

The linearity evaluation was performed with the correlation coefficient (R^2). For the sensitivity evaluation, the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were determined by signal-to-noise ratio, with acceptable ratios of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively.

2.6.2. Extraction recovery

Extraction recovery was estimated at three different concentration levels, low quality control (LQC), medium quality control (MQC) and high quality control (HQC), by spiking fecal samples, with a standard solution containing all the examined Short Chain Fatty Acids, before and after the extraction procedure. These levels were determined based on reference ranges observed in healthy individuals and concentrations documented in literature. Due to the substantial differences in endogenous concentrations, such as acetic acid constituting roughly 60% of the total SCFAs, the spiking levels were individually adjusted for each acid. The final concentrations in $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of Low, Medium and High QCs, respectively, for each acid were as follows: acetic acid (10.66, 21.32, 29.98 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), propionic acid (2.16, 4.32, 6.48 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), isobutyric acid (0.23, 0.45, 0.68 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), butyric acid (3.63, 6.36, 8.17 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), isovaleric acid (0.05, 0.10, 0.16 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), valeric acid (0.10, 0.23, 0.39 $\mu\text{mol/g}$). This adjustment allowed the accurate extraction recovery evaluation across the varying concentration ranges of the SCFAs. The recovery was calculated based on the following Eq. (1). Typically, recovery values in the range of 70–120% were considered acceptable.

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{\text{Peak Area spiked before extraction}}{\text{Peak Area spiked after extraction}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Eq. 1: Calculation of extraction recovery.

2.6.3. Precision and accuracy

Accuracy and precision were evaluated through inter- and intra-batch analysis, utilizing fecal samples spiked at the three distinct concentration levels: low (LQC), medium (MQC), and high (HQC). As different fecal samples were used across experiments (paragraph 2.6.2),

Fig. 1. Final sample preparation workflow; from sample collection to GC-MS analysis.

the final QC concentrations varied and were dependent on the endogenous SCFA levels of each matrix. Three replicates of LQC, MQC and HQC samples, each containing all the examined SCFAs, were analyzed on the same day to assess intra-day reproducibility and on three consecutive days to evaluate inter-day precision. The accuracy of the method was calculated as the percentage ratio of the mean experimental value (after subtracting the endogenous concentration) to the nominal value, expressed as R%. Precision was evaluated by computing the percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) for both intra- and inter-day measurements. Accuracy (%R) was required to be within 80–120% of nominal concentrations at the LOQ and within 85–115% at medium, and high QCs, while precision (%RSD) was not to exceed 20% at the LOQ and 15% at the other QC levels, in accordance with FDA and ICH guidelines.

2.6.4. Stability

Fecal sample stability was evaluated under different storage and transport conditions through three distinct experiments. All storage parameters were carefully controlled: samples were stored in airtight, sealed containers, maintained at defined temperatures (−80 °C, 4 °C, or 20–22 °C) under stable laboratory humidity, and protected from light and excessive air exposure; acidification was treated as an experimental variable and systematically evaluated within the study.

The first experiment assessed short- and long-term stability of real fecal samples across four storage conditions, namely room temperature (RT), refrigerator at 4 °C, and freezer at −20 °C and −80 °C, over multiple time points (Day 1–7, 30, 270 and 365), to monitor both short- and long-term changes. The second evaluated the short-term stability of fecal extracts under typical laboratory storage conditions, while the third investigated the impact of transport-related conditions on real fecal samples.

For the stability of SCFAs, fecal samples spiked at low (LQC), medium (MQC), and high (HQC) quality control levels, were analyzed within 24 h post-collection, designated as Day 0, to establish baseline values. Quantification of the samples was performed using freshly prepared calibration curves. Results were expressed as %Error relative to Day 0 (eq. 2), enabling direct comparison across time points and storage conditions to assess analyte integrity in the short-term, medium-term, and long-term.

$$\%relative\ error = \frac{Concentration\ of\ stability\ experiment - Concentration(Day\ 0)}{Concentration(Day\ 0)} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2: Calculation of stability expressed as % relative error.

Additional stability evaluations of the fecal extracts were conducted after 24 h and 48 h under three storage conditions: 1. in the autosampler, at temperature corresponding to room temperature (approximately 21 °C), 2. refrigerated at 4 °C, and 3. frozen at −20 °C. Results for extract stability were expressed as a percentage of the total concentration, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of relative stability under conditions commonly encountered in laboratory workflows.

Beyond assessing stability under controlled laboratory conditions, an additional experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of transport conditions on fecal metabolite stability. For this purpose, fecal samples were collected immediately after voiding, with baseline values established from samples analyzed at this initial time point (0 h). Following the best storage practices for metabolites analysis, samples were stored at −80 °C within one hour of collection [24]. To simulate transport conditions and assess potential degradation, a subset of samples was stored at room temperature (RT) for three days, followed by seven days at −20 °C. Additionally, another subset was stored at RT in an acidic aqueous solution for ten days to evaluate an alternative stabilization

approach. Metabolite concentrations, expressed in μmol/g, were compared to baseline values to assess stability under different transport conditions. This study provides insights into sample integrity outside optimal storage conditions, complementing laboratory-based stability assessments.

2.7. Application of the method

Forty healthy adult volunteers were recruited and provided written informed consent prior to participation. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics and Deontology Committee of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, (Protocol ID 312909/2025 and 9398/2026). All procedures complied with the Declaration of Helsinki and relevant national/European regulations. Participant confidentiality was maintained throughout, and samples were coded to ensure anonymization. Study samples were extracted by the optimized extraction protocol with 1:2 (w) sample/(v) solvent of MTBE 15% H₃PO₄.

Quantifications were performed based on the external calibration curve.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. GC-MS method development

GC-MS analytical conditions were systematically optimized by testing various thermal gradients and injection parameters to achieve sharp peak shapes and adequate chromatographic separation of the analytes. Due to the high volatility of the compounds, acetic acid, the earliest eluting analyte, was observed to co-elute with the solvent front, leading to inaccuracies in quantification. To address this, the temperature program described in Section 2.3 was selected, as it provided improved resolution and reliable quantification, albeit at the expense of a longer overall analysis time. This optimized method was subsequently applied throughout the study. Retention times of the analytes are presented in Table 1.

3.2. Sample preparation optimization

3.2.1. Selection of extraction method

Regarding the extraction solvent results, ethyl acetate generated interfering background signals in the chromatograms of acetic acid, most likely originating from partial hydrolysis of the solvent under the applied analytical conditions, thereby compromising selectivity. Hexane exhibited poor extraction efficiency for the targeted Short-Chain Fatty Acids, reflecting its low polarity and limited miscibility with the aqueous fecal matrix. Although diethyl ether showed improved extraction relative to hexane, its high volatility and associated handling difficulties reduced its practicality for routine analysis. MTBE was ultimately selected as the extraction solvent, as it provided the highest extraction recoveries across the analytes of interest, while minimizing background interference and offering better operational robustness. This choice ensured both analytical reliability and reproducibility for the subsequent application of the method. The extraction efficacy of each solvent using a neat standard is presented in Fig. 2.

Different fecal-to-solvent extraction ratios (1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4, w/v) were systematically assessed, with the 1:2 ratio yielding the highest extraction efficiency and overall reproducibility. The addition of anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄) to the organic phase was investigated as a

Table 1

Linear equations, coefficient of determination (R^2) of the external calibration curves and limits of detection (LOD, $\mu\text{mol/g}$) and quantification (LOQ, $\mu\text{mol/g}$) of each SCFA.

SCFAs	tR (min)	Slope	Intercept	R^2	Linearity Range ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)
Acetic Acid	11.5	235,796	201,815	0.9999	1.56–199.80	0.52	1.50
Propionic Acid	12.6	360,081	8698.4	0.9999	0.63–80.99	0.21	0.60
Isobutyric Acid	13.0	277,858	17,128	0.9995	0.43–13.62	0.40	0.40
Butyric Acid	13.7	1,000,000	2,000,000	0.9968	0.7–45.40	0.23	0.70
Isovaleric Acid	14.2	544,953	15,496	0.9997	0.03–3.92	0.01	0.03
Valeric Acid	15.2	1,000,000	20,335	1.0000	0.03–3.92	0.01	0.03

Fig. 2. Peak area of SCFAs in standard solution using MTBE and ethyl acetate as extraction solvents. The secondary y-axis displays isobutyric's peak areas. Data are presented as mean \pm SD based on triplicate measurements ($n = 3$).

Fig. 3. Peak area of SCFAs across the different fecal water and extraction solvent ratios. Data are presented as mean \pm SD based on triplicate measurements ($n = 3$).

mean of removing residual water; however, this step did not produce a significant effect on peak areas, indicating that residual moisture was not a critical factor under the applied conditions. A double-extraction procedure was also evaluated, but resulted in lower signal intensities, particularly for SCFAs at low concentrations, most likely due to dilution effects associated with the increased solvent volume. On this basis, a single extraction at a 1:2 ratio was selected as the optimal protocol (Fig. 3).

3.2.2. Acidification reagent selection

To facilitate efficient extraction of SCFAs into the organic phase, it

was necessary to convert the analytes to their non-ionized (protonated) form by adjusting the extraction solution to a pH below 2. This adjustment was guided by the pKa values of the SCFAs, ensuring that the acids remained predominantly in their protonated, more hydrophobic state, thereby enhancing partitioning into the organic solvent. Among the acidification reagents, 15% v/v H_3PO_4 provided the most effective protonation, yielding consistent peak areas and stable chromatographic performance. Subsequently, different volumes of 15% H_3PO_4 (10–50 μL) were tested, with 20 μL identified as optimal; larger volumes did not further decrease the pH and offered no additional benefit. This condition was therefore selected for all subsequent extractions.

3.2.3. Homogenization test

To optimize sample preparation for SCFA extraction, different homogenization techniques were compared. Comparative analysis of the resulting peak areas revealed no statistically significant differences among the tested approaches. Given its shorter processing time and equivalent extraction performance, the two-cycle Bead Mill homogenization method (30 s per cycle at 6 m/s) was selected as the preferred procedure for subsequent analyses.

3.2.4. Intra-sample variation

Collecting, homogenizing, and storing the entire fecal evacuation is often impractical, thus, small portions of stool are typically sampled for analysis. However, such subsampling may introduce analytical bias due to intra-sample heterogeneity. To assess this effect, SCFAs concentrations were compared between fully homogenized control samples and subsamples taken from four distinct regions (top, middle, bottom, and edge) of non-homogenized stool. As shown in Fig. 4, SCFAs levels varied significantly depending on the sampling location, demonstrating substantial spatial variability within a single specimen. These findings highlight the importance of thorough homogenization prior to extraction to ensure representative and reproducible quantification of SCFAs.

3.3. Method validation

3.3.1. Calibration and linearity

Quantification of endogenous compounds typically relies on calibration methods, such as standard addition, where fortification of the biological matrix is used to account for matrix effects. However, due to the inherent heterogeneity of fecal samples, it is impractical to perform a standard addition calibration for each batch of analysis. This would require individual calibration for each sample, which is not feasible given the high variability and number of samples typically analyzed.

Moreover, the absence of a universally accepted reference standard material for feces, complicates the establishment of a robust standard calibration procedure. Given these limitations, the use of an external calibration curve seemed to be the most practical approach.

In the present study, both a standard addition curve and an external calibration curve were used to assess the extent of the matrix effects, by comparing their parallelism over the working concentration ranges. For all compounds, the slope ratios ranged between 0.88 and 1.1 (supplementary material) and were considered acceptable, indicating negligible matrix effects, thereby supporting the use of an external calibration curve for the quantification of SCFAs.

Extracted ion chromatograms (EICs) of individual SCFAs in a fortified sample are presented in Figure S1.

Results from the method's linearity assessment and sensitivity, based on external calibration curves for each SCFA, are presented in Table 1. All Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) exhibited strong linearity with correlation coefficients (R^2) exceeding 0.99. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were established at signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively, reflecting acceptable sensitivity levels. The LODs for the SCFAs ranged from 0.01 to 0.52 $\mu\text{mol/g}$. The

Fig. 4. Spatial variability of total SCFA content within a fecal sample.

Table 2

Extraction recovery (RE%) calculated in three concentration levels for the six SCFAs.

Compound	Spiked Concentration ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	RE%
Acetic Acid	10.66	97
	21.32	93
	29.98	88
Propionic Acid	2.16	94
	4.32	107
	6.48	111
Isobutyric Acid	0.23	77
	0.45	79
	0.68	66
Butyric Acid	3.63	99
	6.36	104
	8.17	93
Isovaleric Acid	0.05	99
	0.10	95
	0.16	91
Valeric Acid	0.10	92
	0.23	97
	0.39	90

calibration curves for all SCFAs are provided in the supplementary material (Figure S2).

3.3.2. Extraction recovery (RE)

Recovery was calculated for all Short Chain Fatty Acids in three concentration levels, and the results are presented in Table 2. The results for all compounds, except isobutyric acid were within acceptable limits in accordance with EU guidelines.

Isobutyric acid showed significantly lower recovery efficiency compared to the other SCFAs, especially at higher concentrations. This is likely due to its poor stability and its low endogenous levels in feces, which may contribute to higher variability and cause challenges in achieving consistent recoveries.

3.3.3. Accuracy and intra-day and inter-day precision

Accuracy and precision of the method were evaluated within a day and over a span of three days. Values for intra-day accuracy ranged from 97.6% (propionic acid) to 112.4% (isobutyric acid) at LQC, from 81.4% (isovaleric acid) to 109.9% (acetic acid) at MQC and from 75.2% (isovaleric acid) to 107.8% (acetic acid) at HQC. Inter-day accuracy spanned from 99% (valeric acid) to 108% (butyric acid) for LQC, from 84% (isovaleric acid) to 98% (acetic acid) for MQC and from 81% (isovaleric acid) to 95% (acetic acid) for HQC. The respective precision for inter-day experiments expressed in %RSD varied between 7% (butyric acid) and 15% (acetic acid) for LQC, 4% (acetic acid) and 10% (isobutyric acid) for MQC and 7% (acetic and propionic acid) and 11% (isovaleric acid) for HQC. All intra and inter-day experimental data can be found in Table 3.

3.3.4. Stability

Feces are a complex and sensitive matrix, with ongoing microbial activity, which can influence metabolite concentrations over time. Since SCFAs are the end products of anaerobic microbial metabolism, their levels can fluctuate depending on storage conditions, potentially affecting their accurate quantification. In order to assess these variations, a stability experiment was conducted, monitoring SCFAs concentrations over a defined period under different storage conditions, as described in Section 2.6.4. The experimental data are graphically represented in Fig. 5.

The % error was calculated relative to the initial concentration (day 0). Values approaching -100% indicate complete loss of the analyte, corresponding to extensive degradation or concentrations falling below the detection limit. Conversely, positive values (up to $+100\%$) reflect an apparent increase in SCFA levels, which may be attributed to ongoing microbial activity, continued fermentation, or release of bound SCFAs

Table 3
Mean concentrations, accuracy (R%) and %RSDs at the examined concentrations for each SCFA.

Analytes	Cnom ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	DAY 1 (n = 3)			Day 2 (n = 3)			Day 3 (n = 3)			Inter-Day (n = 3 \times 3)		
		Mean \pm SD	Accuracy (%R)	% RSD	Mean \pm SD	Accuracy (%R)	% RSD	Mean \pm SD	Accuracy (%R)	% RSD	Mean \pm SD	Accuracy (%R)	% RSD
Acetic Acid	5.0	5.4 \pm 0.67	108.1	12	4.9 \pm 0.81	98.6	16	5.9 \pm 0.92	111.4	15	5.4 \pm 0.8	106	15
Propionic Acid	4.5	4.7 \pm 0.26	104.1	6	4.4 \pm 0.54	98.2	12	4.4 \pm 0.38	97.6	9	4.5 \pm 0.39	100	9
Isobutyric Acid	0.75	0.96 \pm 0.14	106.3	15	0.75 \pm 0.04	100.3	5	0.84 \pm 0.03	112.4	3	0.85 \pm 0.07	106	8
Butyric Acid	2.0	2.4 \pm 0.22	106	9	2.2 \pm 0.13	108.4	6	2.2 \pm 0.14	110.6	7	2.3 \pm 0.16	108	7
Isovaleric Acid	1.0	0.99 \pm 0.08	98.7	8	1 \pm 0.15	101.9	15	1 \pm 0.08	104.2	8	1 \pm 0.11	102	10
Valeric Acid	0.75	0.79 \pm 0.04	105.4	5	0.71 \pm 0.11	94.6	15	0.74 \pm 0.04	98.2	6	0.75 \pm 0.07	99	9
Acetic Acid	10.0	9.1 \pm 0.58	91	6	9.4 \pm 0.1	94.1	1	11 \pm 0.5	109.9	5	9.8 \pm 0.4	98	4
Propionic Acid	9.0	7.9 \pm 0.55	87.5	7	7.8 \pm 0.28	86.6	4	8.6 \pm 0.41	95	5	8.1 \pm 0.41	90	5
Isobutyric Acid	1.5	1.5 \pm 0.24	100.8	16	1.4 \pm 0.01	90.3	1	1.4 \pm 0.19	91.7	14	1.4 \pm 0.14	94	10
Butyric Acid	4.0	3.4 \pm 0.21	87.8	6	3.9 \pm 0.07	97.5	2	3.8 \pm 0.37	94.2	10	3.7 \pm 0.22	93	6
Isovaleric Acid	2.0	1.5 \pm 0.11	81.4	8	1.6 \pm 0.06	83.1	4	1.7 \pm 0.06	87.2	3	1.6 \pm 0.08	84	5
Valeric Acid	1.5	1.3 \pm 0.09	84.1	7	1.2 \pm 0.03	82.4	3	1.2 \pm 0.19	87.4	16	1.2 \pm 0.1	85	8
Acetic Acid	20.0	17.4 \pm 0.25	87.1	1	18.3 \pm 1.8	91.5	10	21.6 \pm 2.18	107.8	10	19.1 \pm 1.4	95	7
Propionic Acid	18.0	16.1 \pm 0.78	89.2	5	15.9 \pm 1.5	92.7	9	17.4 \pm 1.3	96.8	7	16.5 \pm 1.2	93	7
Isobutyric Acid	3.0	2.6 \pm 0.3	88.2	11	2.5 \pm 0.2	85.4	8	2.7 \pm 0.18	89.4	7	2.6 \pm 0.22	88	9
Butyric Acid	8.0	6.9 \pm 0.72	86.1	10	6.8 \pm 0.89	91.2	13	7.8 \pm 0.56	97.2	7	7.2 \pm 0.72	91	10
Isovaleric Acid	4.0	2.8 \pm 0.21	75.2	8	2.8 \pm 0.35	78.8	13	3.4 \pm 0.41	90.1	12	3 \pm 0.33	81	11
Valeric Acid	3.0	2.4 \pm 0.16	84.7	7	2.2 \pm 0.25	82.2	11	2.6 \pm 0.29	93.2	11	2.4 \pm 0.23	87	10

within the fecal matrix during storage. Across all SCFAs, samples stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ exhibited minimal variability throughout the 365-day study, confirming this as the most reliable condition for long-term stability. In contrast, samples kept at room temperature showed pronounced variability and rapid degradation, with errors exceeding $\pm 50\%$ within the first few days. Refrigerated storage at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ maintained acceptable stability for up to 4–5 days; however, beyond this period, marked deviations were observed, particularly for isobutyric and isovaleric acids, which displayed the greatest instability. Storage at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ preserved most SCFAs with acceptable accuracy for up to 30 days, though a progressive decline in quantification accuracy was evident thereafter, especially for propionic and butyric acids. Notably, acetic and valeric acids were comparatively more stable across conditions, while branched SCFAs (isobutyric and isovaleric) showed the highest susceptibility to degradation. These findings indicate that fecal samples should be analyzed within 30 days when stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and within 4–5 days under refrigeration ($4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), whereas storage at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is essential for accurate long-term SCFA quantification.

During validation experiments, significant fluctuations in SCFAs measurements were observed, especially when analysis times were prolonged, particularly in large sample batches. This raised concerns about extract stability over time and whether storage conditions could affect their overall integrity. To further evaluate this, an additional experiment was carried out, as described in Section 2.6.4. The experimental data are graphically presented in Fig. 6.

A pronounced decline in peak area was observed in extracts stored in the autosampler, with complete signal loss by 48 h, indicating severe degradation. In contrast, extracts stored at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ exhibited

more gradual decreases in signal intensity, with comparable areas remaining after 48 h. These results highlight the critical impact of storage temperature on extract stability. Notably, refrigeration at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ appears sufficient for maintaining SCFA extract integrity for short-term delays in analysis (up to 48 h), while autosampler conditions should be avoided for prolonged storage due to rapid compound degradation. All measurements were conducted in triplicate, with relative standard deviation (RSD) values below 15%, indicating acceptable analytical precision.

In addition to the long-term stability study, a short-term stability experiment was designed to simulate transport conditions, recognizing that fecal samples are not always processed immediately after collection. Samples were stored under different conditions for up to 10 days, as outlined in Section 2.6.5, with the aim of identifying storage strategies that minimize metabolic alterations and preserve SCFA content. Total SCFA concentrations remained largely comparable to baseline (control, time 0) when samples were kept for 10 days in acidic solution at room temperature, indicating that acidification provides effective stabilization during transport. Samples exposed to room temperature for 3 days followed by transfer to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 7 days also retained SCFA levels comparable, or slightly higher, than controls, suggesting this approach is suitable when immediate freezing is delayed. By contrast, samples frozen at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ within 1 h of collection and analyzed after 10 days showed lower SCFA concentrations relative to the control, consistent with potential analyte loss during freeze-thaw or prolonged storage. Overall, these findings suggest that controlled acidification or a short delay at room temperature prior to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ freezing are practical strategies to preserve SCFA integrity during sample transport (Figure S3).

Fig. 5. Stability of SCFAs in fecal samples stored under different conditions (room temperature, 4 °C, -20 °C, and -80 °C) over 1–365 days.

3.4. Analysis of fecal samples

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the method, 40 fecal samples from healthy individuals were analyzed to quantify the Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) of interest. SCFAs are central microbial metabolites, which are influenced by several factors, including diet, microbiota composition and host metabolism. Despite these variations, a distinctive profile was observed with acetic acid, propionic acid and butyric acid being the predominant SCFAs in all samples. These findings are aligned with previous studies highlighting their essential role in gut health, energy metabolism and immune regulation.

In total six SCFAs were detected and quantified in all analyzed samples. Among the detected SCFAs, acetic acid was found at highest levels, ranging from 23.9 to 134.6 $\mu\text{mol/g}$, followed by propionic (4.9–45 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) and butyric (2.0–57.3 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) acids. This aligns with its widespread production pathways across multiple bacterial species, making it the most abundant SCFA produced in the gut. Lower concentrations were observed for isobutyric (0.4–11.4 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), isovaleric (0.4–20 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) and valeric (0.2–8.6 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) acids. Due to substantial concentration differences among SCFAs, a logarithmic scale was applied for visualization, ensuring a more accurate representation of the data distribution (Fig. 7).

The density distributions reveal that acetic acid levels exhibit greater inter-individual variability compared to the other SCFAs. In contrast, propionic and butyric acids distributions are shown to be more concentrated, while isobutyric, isovaleric and valeric acids are present at considerably lower levels, with narrower distributions, indicating less variability in their production.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed and validated a sensitive, accurate, and reproducible GC–MS method for the quantification of Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) in human fecal samples. By eliminating the derivatization step, the method substantially streamlines sample preparation, while maintaining high recovery rates and analytical robustness. This simplification not only reduces processing time, but also minimizes the potential for analytical errors arising from multi-step derivatization procedures, making the approach highly suitable for routine laboratory use and translational clinical applications.

Stability experiments demonstrated that SCFAs remain stable in crude fecal samples stored in aqueous acidic solution for at least 10 days, without cold-chain requirements, facilitating large-scale and field-based studies, while optimal long-term preservation is achieved at -80 °C and short-term storage (up to 4–5 days) is feasible at 4 °C. The method achieved low limits of detection (LODs) (0.01–0.52 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), outperforming previously reported non-derivatized GC–MS approaches and offering a practical balance between sensitivity, reproducibility, and operational efficiency, despite slightly higher sensitivity reported for derivatized methods. Additionally, the observed intra-sample variability across different stool regions highlights the critical importance of sample homogenization to ensure representative and reproducible measurements. Overall, this validated method provides a practical, scalable, and efficient tool for SCFA analysis, supporting applications in microbiome research, biomarker discovery, clinical studies, and large-scale epidemiological investigations aimed at elucidating the role of gut microbial metabolism in human health and disease.

Fig. 6. Line plots depicting the stability of extracts across the different storage conditions and time points.

Fig. 7. Violin plots representing SCFAs levels in real samples.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Virgiliou Chistina: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Gika Helen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Theodoridis Georgios:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision,

Investigation. **Begou Olga:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Farantatou Konstantina:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Gkanali Vasiliki:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Informed consent statement

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects enrolled in the study.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jpba.2026.117488](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2026.117488).

Data availability

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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